

CONTRIBUTION OF RUDYARD KIPLING AS A WRITER OF CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the contribution of Rudyard Kipling as a writer of Children's Literature. Works by Rudyard Kipling, one of the most famous British writers of the twentieth century, remain as current and fresh in the present times as they were a century ago. Kipling's power as writer can be estimated from the highly prestigious reputation that his works still enjoy in the present academia and the present generation of readers. Kipling tired his hand at almost all forms of English literature including poems, short stories, novels and children's books. His language is rich, inventive, and sonorous. His fame chiefly rests upon the stories he wrote for children. These stories can be grouped under three categories-Animal Tales - The Jungle Book (1894), The Second Jungle Book (1895) and Just so Stories (1902), School Tales - Stalky&Co (1899) and Historical Tales Puck of Pook's Hill (1906) and Reward and Fairies (1910). Jungle Book went on to become one of the bestsellers in the history of English. In this paper I will be exploring why Kipling's animal narratives like Jungle Books and Just so stories, historical tales like Puck of the Pook's Hill and Rewards and Fairies, and School Tales as Stalky & Co. remain as unforgettable and popular children's classics in English even today.

Keywords : Rudyard Kipling, Children's Literature, Contribution

Children's Literature has been a much neglected area and has struggled a lot to gain its popularity and footings in the world literary canon. Early Children's Literature consisted of spoken stories, songs, and poems, that were used to educate, instruct, and entertain children. The development of early Children's Literature, before printing was invented, is difficult to trace. It was only in the 18th century, with the development of the concept of "childhood" that a separate genre of Children's Literature began to emerge, with its own divisions and expectations. The late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries became known as the "Golden Age of Children's Literature" as this period included the publication of many books acknowledged today as classics. This age was particularly dominated by authors, namely Thomas Hughes, Lewis Carroll, Charles Kingsley, J. M. Barrie, Mark Twain, George MacDonald, Robert Louis Stevenson and Rudyard Kipling. Kipling wrote some of the best animal stories for children, including his Jungle

Books and Just So stories.

Credited with popularizing the short story genre in England, Kipling is perhaps most famous for his insightful stories of Indian culture and Anglo-Indian society. Kipling was born in Bombay, India, to English parents. The reflections of his childhood years are felt on every page he wrote about India. At the beginning of his book *Something of Myself*, he has said "Give me the first six years of a child's life and you can have the rest" (Kipling 3). At the age of six, his happy childhood came to an abrupt end. Kipling was sent with his sister to England to live with the Holloway couple at Southsea. Kipling hated his foster home, which he later referred to as the "House of Desolation". This period of desolation, abandonment and misery left unhealed marks on Rudyard's character.

After living with the couple for five years, he was admitted in a new institution called The United Service College at Devon. It was the school which provided him

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with the material for his schoolboy stories entitled *Stalky & Co.* In 1892 Kipling married Balestier's sister Carrie in London. He settled at a house named Bliss Cottage in United States. It was at Bliss Cottage Vermont, where his two daughters were born. There he wrote his first books for children: the two *Jungle Books*. These were his most popular and best-selling books. The short stories written in Vermont initiate a phase of Kipling's career in which he can be considered as having become a writer for children

Rudyard Kipling's *Jungle Books* are a blessed province of fancy and imagination. He wrote the stories with extraordinary power of imagination and flashes of unforgettable description virtuosity. These books were experiments in a new field. He had written a wolf-story called *Mowgli's Brothers*. The impulse was derived from a scene in Rider Haggard's Zulu romance *Nada, the Lily* where in a riot of supernatural fantasy, Umslopogaas is presented as running with a pack of wolves. This was the beginning of his train of thought. Rudyard Kipling elaborated this powerful myth in the first and second *Jungle Book*. This is a story of a man-child called Mowgli who is lost in the jungle. Separated from his real parents as every child both dreads and longs to be, Mowgli is adopted and nurtured by a magically 'other' family, which yet retains the names and ties of the human original. This child soon becomes master of the *Jungle* but he cannot resolve the dilemma of his ambivalent life.

The book describes Indian animal lore, the strange ethical concept called 'The Law of *Jungle*'. The aspect of Law in the *Jungle Books* is Kipling's honest attempt to explain the importance of Law and the necessity of obeying it. For Kipling, the obeying of this Law makes way for order and harmony. It was his bold creative stroke to make his fictional child not half-animal but wholly human – clever, resourceful and keen to learn the “laws” of the jungle, as distinct from the laws of Western society. Kipling has presented the Bandar-log as a direct contrast to the *Jungle* virtuousness. Their dangerous futility is brought out by their doings at Cold Lairs. Baloo and Bagheera are beloved animals in the jungle who are companions of the Man-cub, Mowgli. They are also the mouthpieces of Law. They teach morals to Mowgli and so to the children reading *The Jungle Books*. Kipling has

skillfully portrayed the code of Behaviour in the *Jungle* by making it acceptable to human beings.

Another important aspect of the *Jungle Books* which comes almost on the surface is Kipling's close observation of India and his descriptions of the Indian lifestyle. Rudyard Kipling had a power to make men see what he saw. He poured out into his tales what he knew about India and what he saw in India. He embraced everything in the *Jungle Books* from palaces of Oodeypore to the Himalayan Heights. He used his knowledge about India in his writings. His travels around India had deepened his knowledge of her. He relished the strange scenes he had seen in his works. He had a profound knowledge of Indian life and character. He had studied Indian ways, languages, trades and customs. He was extraordinarily accurate in his Indian details. With Mowgli's return to the Man-pack, Kipling enters into Indian households and does not forget to portray the paraphernalia of Messua's house. It is new to Mowgli as well as to the people for whom India is a riddle. “Red lacquered bedstead, a great earthen grain-chest with curious patterns on it, copper working pots, looking glass, image of Hindu god in a little alcove”(Kipling 81). He has unravelled everything he could about India in his *Jungle Books* and that too, with supreme gift of narrating and in a surprising and dramatic fashion. Kipling does not fail to refer to the celebrated ignorance of the Indians “but India is one place in the world where a man can do as he pleases and nobody asks why” (Kipling 117).

Stalky & Co. is a book published in 1899 (following serialisation in the *Windsor Magazine*) by Rudyard Kipling, about adolescent boys at a British boarding school. Kipling puts himself into the book as the central character called Beetle, he was sent to the United Services College almost by chance, because the headmaster, Cornell Price, was a family friend. He hated the school because he was bullied by the other boys. As a series of stories, *Stalky & Co.* scores over most other school stories because it keeps up interest and emotional intensity in energetic bursts of narrative, each complete in itself, each worked out to make a satisfactory pattern. Most school stories sag because their plots are not interesting or convincing enough to keep up interest or

conviction long enough. *Stalky & Co.* has the same characters and situations throughout but very different things happen to them in each chapter. Each story, or nearly each one, is a carefully constructed tale of retribution, or who it is who gets it. Its outlook, its central characters, its ideals and ideas, still hold lessons for us today. The world it belonged to may have gone, but the points it makes still have relevance to ours.

Stalky & Co. is the only school story which shows school as a direct preparation for life. Most others actually make the world outside school seem irrelevant, an anticlimax, an unimaginable void. Kipling, for all his intense feeling for the school atmosphere and the moods of adolescence, shows school as the first stage of a much larger game, a pattern-maker for the experiences of life. This is mainly what makes it unlike the others, with their narrow, school-centred preoccupations and their belief, often implied and sometimes even stated, in the overwhelming importance of this preliminary stage of life, which was actually presumed to outdo the rest in importance. In Kipling, not only is a later life envisaged very clearly at school, but the divisions between school and the world outside are less clearly defined than they are in most other school stories. The school teaches the boys how to live; but above all, the boys teach one another.

In 1901 Kipling published the best-selling novel, *Kim*. Riding on the success of *Kim*, over the next few years Kipling concentrated on writing children's books such as *Just So Stories* (1902), *Puck of Pook's Hill* (1906) and *Rewards and Fairies* (1910). *Kim* has indeed been considered Kipling's Masterpiece by many critics. It happened to be the first Indian President Jawahar Lal Nehru's favourite book. It was specifically in *Kim* that "Kipling has established the contrast between the East, with its mysticism and its sensuality, its extremes of saintliness and roguery, and the English, with their superior organization, their confidence in modern method, their instinct to brush away like cobwebs the native myths and beliefs... we have watched the oscillations of *Kim*, as he passes to and fro between them." (Belliappa and Myers 100). *Kim* shows Kipling's sensitivity towards India.

The novel, *Kim* is notable for its detailed portrait of the people, culture, and varied religions of India. "The book presents a vivid picture of India, its teeming populations, religions, and superstitions, and the life of the bazaars and the road." The novel depicts the world of a half-Irish white boy finding his way amid the many religious, cultural, and political factions vying for power in India at the turn of the 20th century. The philosophical, religious, and historical concepts presented in the novel are complex, and will be best understood by teens and adults. The main character in *Kim*, is Kimball O'Hara, a poor half-Irish boy growing up on the streets of Lahore, India, living off of his wits and keen powers of observation. *Kim* becomes the "chela," or disciple, of Teshoo Lama, a Tibetan lama who is on a spiritual journey to find the "River of the Arrow." While traveling with the lama, *Kim* meets a regiment of Irish soldiers who are joined with the British in the Great Game, an ongoing military/political conflict between the British and Russians over power in central Asia. The Irish chaplain sees that *Kim* is wearing an amulet associated with their regiment and makes the connection that *Kim*'s father was Irish. Once it is noticed that *Kim* is white, the struggle for *Kim*'s allegiance begins to parallel the cultural conflicts going on in colonial India, revealing much about the country and setting up some difficult choices for the boy.

Among the reasons *Kim* is so widely revered are the vast amount of cultural and religious ground the novel covers and the brilliant way Kipling embodies political conflict within his main character. This novel is beautifully written and structured -- with relevant and lyrical poems beginning each chapter -- and always stays grounded in the relatable experience of the bright young boy *Kim*. This is a fascinating choice for teens who are intrigued by world cultures and religions, and an important book, as well, for students of literature and history.

Rudyard Kipling told his children gloriously fanciful tales of how things in the world came to be as they are. He wrote them down for publication as the *Just So Stories* in 1902. Kipling began working on the book by telling the first three chapters as bedtime stories to his daughter Josephine. The stories describe how one animal

or another acquired its most distinctive features, such as how the leopard got his spots. 'How the Camel Got His Hump' and 'How the Leopard Got his Spots'. The Just So Stories typically have the theme of a particular animal being modified from an original form to its current form by the acts of man, or some magical being. For example, the Whale has a tiny throat because he swallowed a mariner, who tied a raft inside to block the whale from swallowing other men. Similarly, the Camel has a hump given to him by a djinn as punishment for the camel's refusing to work and so on. They are written in an amusing grand style, peppered with long, and delightfully unlikely, invented words - a comical exaggeration perhaps of the formal ways of speaking Kipling heard in India. Each story includes a short poem, and the first edition features Kipling's own illustrations. Throughout the book he addresses the reader as "Best Beloved", reinforcing the intimacy of story-telling and recalling the first 'best beloved: his lost daughter, Josephine.

Puck of Pook's Hill is a fantasy book by Rudyard Kipling, published in 1906, containing a series of short stories set in different periods of English history. It can be counted both as historical fantasy – since some of the stories told of the past have clear magical elements, and as contemporary fantasy – since it depicts a magical being active and practising his magic in the England of the early 1900s when the book was written. The stories are all narrated to two children living near Burwash, in the area of Kipling's own house Bateman's, by people magically plucked out of history by the elf Puck, or told by Puck himself. (Puck, who refers to himself as "the oldest Old Thing in England", is better known as a character in William Shakespeare's play *A Midsummer Night's Dream*.) Each story is bracketed by a poem which relates in some manner to the theme or subject of the story. Donald Mackenzie, who wrote the introduction for the Oxford World's Classics edition of *Puck of Pook's Hill* in 1987, has described this book as an example of archaeological imagination that, in fragments, delivers a look at the history of England, climaxing with the signing of Magna Carta.

'Rewards and Fairies' is a sequel to 'Puck of Pook's

Hill' but it can be read independently, since only a few tales use characters from the first book and when they do, all the references work only to situate those who read the first book and are not important for the understanding of the plot. Besides, the story's frame presented in the first book is covered in this book's introduction, thus closing all possible loose ends. The book consists of a series of short stories set in historical times with a linking contemporary narrative. All these tales are lightly told, but some of its meaning likely goes beyond the understanding of most children, making this book a gem for re-reading in mature years.

After a careful and detailed study of the stories that Kipling wrote for children, I have come to the conclusion that even though critics tried to label him as an imperialist yet when it comes to writing for children, he is a genius. Swati Singh in his *Secret History of the Jungle Book*, observes, that Kipling wove "magic and fantasy" into the stories for his daughter Josephine, and that even critics reading Kipling for signs of imperialism could not help admiring the power of his storytelling. The *Jungle Book* written by Kipling is popular even now and has been adapted into many films. The autobiographical elements in his works become evident when one goes back to trace the roots of Kipling's works. The inspiration for the most part comes from his life's events and happenings. Kipling fashioned these tales to be read aloud, and critics agree that the oral beauty of his writing makes these stories particularly memorable.

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